

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF IN-PLANE COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIOUR OF UNSYMMETRICAL SANDWICH PANELS

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Keywords: *unsymmetrical sandwich, impact damage, damage tolerance, CAI strength*

Summary

An experimental study of in-plane compressive behaviour of unsymmetrical composite sandwich panels was conducted. Two skin thickness combinations were 8/6 plies and 16/12 plies. Both cross ply and quasi-isotropic lay-ups were used in each combination. All sandwich panels were impact-damaged and their dominant damage mechanisms were established. All impact-damaged as well as baseline panels were compression tested. The effects of lacking the symmetry, skin thickness and skin lay-up on CAI strength was examined along with the role of the core.

1 Introduction

Composite sandwich structures have been widely used in the aerospace, marine, automotive and railway industries because of their high specific bending stiffness and strength against distributed loads. They have increasingly been expected to be damage-tolerant and energy-absorbing. Under concentrated impact loads, a multitude of damage mechanisms induced affects their subsequent residual in-plane compression (popularly known as compression-after-impact (CAI)) performance. This has highlighted the need for a thorough understanding of the in-plane compressive behaviour of sandwich structures, as the lack of symmetry becomes increasingly an effective way for weight saving.

The research programmes at Loughborough University have been carried out to systematically investigate the in-plane compressive behaviour of intact and impact-damaged composite sandwich panels with both aluminium and nomex honeycombs. In two early reports [1-2], damage

mechanisms in both aluminium and nomex honeycomb sandwich panels induced via both impact and quasi-static loads were ascertained; the effects of skin thickness, core density and material, indenter nose shape, panel diameter and support condition on the damage characteristics were studied. The energy-absorbing characteristics of the identified damage mechanisms were examined. In a subsequent report [3], the in-plane compressive behaviour of intact and impact-damaged symmetric sandwich panels with aluminium honeycomb core was discussed. This paper presents some results of a further investigation of how the lack of symmetry in skins affects the in-plane compressive behaviour of impact-damaged composite sandwich panels.

2 Sandwich materials and panel manufacture

Laminate skins were made of unidirectional carbon/epoxy 34-700/LTM45 prepreg with a ply thickness of 0.128 mm. For symmetrical panels, both cross-ply lay-up of (0/90)_{(2)s} and quasi-isotropic lay-up of (45/0/-45/90)_{(2)s} were used. For unsymmetrical panels, two combinations of skin thicknesses were used with the same ratio of the thicker skins to the thinner skins. One unsymmetrical panel had a combination of 8 plies and 6 plies in their two skins. The other unsymmetrical panel had a combination of 16 plies and 12 plies in their two skins. When the lay-up was quasi-isotropic, the thinner skins were in a multi-directional lay-up of (45/0/-45)_{(2)s}. Honeycomb core of 5052 aluminium had a core depth of 12.7 mm and a density of 70 kg/m³. Adhesive VTA260 was selected for interfacial bonding.

Skin laminates of 300×300 mm were laid up and cured in an autoclave at 60°C under a pressure of 0.62 MPa (90 psi) for 18 hours. The 0° direction of carbon fibres within the skins was aligned with the

ribbon direction of honeycomb core. Each skin was separately bonded to the core in an oven at 60°C for 5 hours under a pressure of 0.1 MPa (15 psi). The sandwich panel was then cut into two nominal 200 mm×150 mm specimens with the longer side aligned with the direction of compressive loading. Back-to-back strain gauges were bonded on the panel surfaces at selected locations in both the longitudinal and transverse directions (see Fig. 2(a)) to monitor mean and panel bending strains. These strain data allowed both local and global behaviour of the panels to be examined.

3 Experimental procedures

3.1 Drop-weight impact tests

Impact tests were carried out on an instrumented drop-weight impact rig shown in Fig. 1 by using a hemispherical impactor of 20 mm diameter with a 1.5 kg mass. Impact energies were regulated by selecting desired drop heights and ranged from 2 J to 60 J in this investigation. Each rectangular carbon/epoxy plate of 200 mm by 150 mm with a circular testing area of 100 mm in diameter was clamped by using a clamping device. Both impact and rebound velocities were measured respectively and this allows absorbed energies to be calculated directly. Impact force was recorded by a data acquisition system. At some selected impact energy levels, one impacted panel conducted was cut up for an examination of damage mechanisms and the other was compression tested.

3.2 In-plane compression test

As part of the compression specimen preparation, the core at the panel ends intended for applying compressive load was removed to a depth of about 5 mm (slightly more than one cell size). Epoxy end pots were cast between the two skins to prevent an end-brooming failure and the two potted ends were machined to parallel. In each in-plane compression test, a panel was placed in a purpose-built support jig, as illustrated in Fig. 2(b). The jig provides simple support along the unloaded edges, which were free to move in the width direction during loading. Quasi-static load was applied to the panel at the machined ends via either a Denison testing machine at less than 0.5 mm/ min. Load, strain and cross-head displacement in all tests were recorded. All tested panels were cut up for study of damage

mechanisms. The loading direction coincided with the 90° direction in the skins of panels.

Fig. 1. Drop-weight impact test rig

Fig. 2. (a) In-plane compression specimen and (b) experimental set-up for compression

4 Damage mechanisms and energy absorption

The initiation and propagation characteristics of damage mechanisms in impacted sandwich panels in

bending were examined extensively via impact response curves, visual observations with the aid of systematic microscopic inspections and cross sectioning. These techniques were shown in [1-3] to be very effective. Thus this approach with the same techniques was deployed for current unsymmetrical sandwich panels. Impact at the lower end of the impact energy range typically produces a surface dent, as shown in Fig. 3. A further increase of impact energy resulted in ply fracture on the impacted skin, as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. A sandwich panel impacted at 35J

Fig. 4. A sandwich panel impacted at 45J

Current cut-up specimens exhibit the salient features from their damage mechanisms very similar to those established in the symmetrical sandwich panels [1-3]. The initial damage was found to be due to core crushing. In some cases, small delamination in the impacted skin was also observed. The initial damage was followed by a continued core crushing with either the onset or propagation of delaminations. Eventually, skin ply fracture occurred. A cross section of a damaged unsymmetrical 16/12 panel (shown in Fig. 3) impacted at 35J is shown in Fig. 5, which shows extensive crushed core and skin

delaminations in the impacted (16-ply) skin. The bottom (12-ply) skin remained intact in all cases and the maximum crushed depths at the upper end of the impact energy ranges reached about the middle of cores at the highest impact energy. This offers some experimental evidence to justify the desire for removing a couple of plies in the distal skin for further weight reduction while maintaining the impact damage resistance. There was no local skin-core debonding. The extent of crushed core was generally greater than the extent of skin delamination. There was no noticeable difference in these characteristics between symmetrical and unsymmetrical panels.

Fig. 5. A sandwich panel impacted at 35J

The energy-absorbing characteristics of the impacted unsymmetrical panels are shown in Fig. 6 for two types of panels with skins in quasi-isotropic and multi-directional lay-ups. In the initial region, a linear increase in energy absorption is around two thirds of impact energy. Once skin fracture occurred, the absorbed energy is increased abruptly up to over 90%. Again, the overall energy-absorbing features of current unsymmetrical panels are very similar to those from the earlier symmetrical panels.

Fig. 6. Energy absorption of sandwich panels

5 Residual in-plane compressive behaviour

The in-plane residual compressive behaviour of the damaged sandwich panels was very complex due primarily to two factors. One is that the sandwich itself was complex structure on its own during in-plane compression because the two skins were stabilised by the core to some degree. When one skin was impact damaged, the 'equal contribution' from the two identical skins to the compression resistance was lost. The lack of skin symmetry in their construction simply adds a significant additional complexity. Thus, a substantial part of prior knowledge and understanding established from the compression of monolithic panels (e.g. in [4-5]) did not apply. The other is that, while the distal thinner skin remained undamaged after impact, the impacted thicker skin around the mid-section region was damaged with core underneath being crushed. The very 'unequal contribution' to the compression resistance initially could be 'evened up' by the impact damage in the thicker skin. Therefore, the residual compressive performance of the damaged panels was attributed not only to the strength degradation of the compressive skin associated with the damage but also to the lack of symmetry for the panels with respect to the in-plane compression loading and supporting conditions and interaction between the skins and core in each of such panels.

As the tolerance assessment of impact damage in sandwich panels is adapted from that for monolithic laminated panels, the role played by the sandwich core in in-plane compression has not been addressed. A nominal width-to-thickness ratio of a sandwich panel is generally much smaller than that of a monolithic panel as its thickness increase is much more than the increase in its length and width. In particular, the presence of the core between the two skins provides a constraint in the through-the-thickness direction to both longitudinally transverse shear and normal compression. As a result, the skins had to overcome the constraint during compressive deformation. This suggests that the compressed skins had to shear the core and crush core first or dimple rather than wrinkle outwards, thereby increasing the compressive resistance. Nearly all the impact-damaged sandwich panels failed around the mid-section region, which was weakened by the presence of impact damage. An example from the

thinner 8/6 panels is shown in Fig. 7, whereas an example from the thicker 16/12 panels is shown in Fig. 8, in which the longitudinal shearing through the core is clearly visible.

Fig. 7. Photographs showing a side view of an impact-damaged sandwich panel after CAI test

Fig. 8. Photographs showing front and side view of an impact-damaged sandwich panel after CAI test

6 Impact damage tolerance

Assessing the effect of impact damage in unsymmetrical sandwich panels in in-plane compression was very difficult, as the lack of symmetry in the sandwich could counteract the effect of impact damage, if the thicker skin is sufficiently damaged. Therefore, a steady reduction trend of CAI strength or strain with an increase of impact energy (IKE) may not be established. This point is clearly shown in Fig. 9 for the thinner unsymmetrical sandwich panels. It is interesting to observe in this figure that these thinner panels were as if very damage-tolerant up to 17 or 18J without suffering any reduction in their CAI strengths. We

believe this is because the benefit of two additional plies in the thicker skins was cancelled out by the impact damage such that the baseline values of in-plane compressive strength were as if more or less unchanged up to about 15J. Around 20 J where ply fracture occurred, CAI strength values have deteriorated further. This implies that the in-plane compressive behaviour of the undamaged unsymmetrical panels may not be as good as those of symmetrical panels. In addition, data from sandwich panels with skins in a lay-up of cross ply seem to show a significant scatter for both baseline and CAI strength values at the lower end of impact energy range. A further examinations of tested panels revealed that the lower strength values were associated with the fact that they failed prematurely at one of the two ends. For the thicker unsymmetrical panels in Fig. 10, a reduction of CAI strength was moderate. Their steady degrading trends are similar to those established for symmetrical sandwich panels in [3]. A further degradation of their CAI strengths after the occurrence of ply fracture is visible but much less obvious. In addition, the effect of lay-up in these thicker unsymmetrical panels on CAI strength is small.

Fig. 9. A variation of residual compressive strength with IKE for sandwich panels

7 Closing remarks

Unsymmetrical composite sandwich panels were impact-damaged at impact energy ranging from 2 J to 60 J. Both intact and impact-damaged panels were subjected subsequently to in-plane compression. The

presence of the core counteracted the deleterious effect of impact damage. While the thicker unsymmetrical panels showed the CAI characteristics similar to symmetrical panels, the thinner panels demonstrated that impact damage in the thicker skin reduced the degree of the effect associated with the lack of symmetry in in-plane compression, thereby enhancing their CAI performance when they were impact-damaged.

Fig. 10. A variation of residual compressive strength for thick unsymmetrical sandwich panels

References

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